

DESIGNING EMOTIONAL TRIGGERS FOR FOOD EXPERIENCES

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ABSTRACT

How often do we hear that eating chocolate, drinking wine or eating our mom's cooking make us feel happy, in peace or even nostalgic? What's the reasoning for our emotional responses? Is there a way to test and validate, from a Design perspective, the emotions evoked in our food experiences? We investigated if it was possible to develop or adapt triggers for emotional food experiences from a Design perspective. Throughout a series of two experiments and a survey, we manipulated taste and sound as the variables on the experiments, while on the survey we asked participants to associate shapes, taste and emotions. Our findings show that intense positive emotional responses were triggered by working around the threshold of discrepancy of expectations. The data also suggests that it is possible to associate shapes, tastes and emotions to a certain extent, and that could be another potential trigger to be further investigated.

Keywords: food experiences; emotional triggers; design emotion; food design; shapes and emotion.

INTRODUCTION

Eating in new, unusual, better and more engaging food experiences. This has been the motto for many consumers around the world due to modern day life, health issues and/or cultural preservation. Alongside the search for better and newer types of food, we also find ourselves searching for better food experiences. Since the time available for sitting down and having a proper meal is getting shorter each day, every experience should count. As designers, how could we

make sure that our end user is getting exactly what he wants and maybe more?

We believe that emotions could be one of the main aspects capable of enhancing food experiences. In order to achieve that, this paper focuses on understanding how emotions could be triggered and how the Design field of research might benefit from it.

EXPERIENCE

Concerning how emotions are or could be elucidated, we will discuss a framework in which such responses may be triggered. The framework used to conceptualize experience is the one proposed by Wright et al (2003) following Dewey's and Bakhtin's theories regarding experiences.

According to the authors, to define experience in a single word or even in a small expression could be naïve. Experience has also been confused with subjective feelings, behavior, activity, social practice, and knowledge. Thus regarding developing an experiential theory, Wright et al quoted Dewey's philosophy of experience, which includes: "what men do and suffer, what they strive for, love, believe and endure, and also how men act and are acted upon, the ways in which they do and suffer, desire and enjoy, see, believe, imagine – in short, processes of experiencing. It is "double barreled" in that it recognizes in its primary integrity no division between act and material, subject and object, but contains them both in an unanalyzed totality" (Dewey, 1925:10-11 IN: Wright et al, 2003:44)

In other words, experience would be the result of the relationship between self and object, where personal interests and beliefs set, partially, the outcome of the experience. The experience itself is fluid, moving, and fragile due to its nature of trusting, identifying,

believing and committing to the moment. Bakhtin (1986, 1993) also focuses his thoughts about experience in terms of quality, where it can be absorbing, captivating, irritating; it is what we experience of ourselves, our culture and our lives. The framework proposed by Wright et al (2003) is composed by four threads:

- 1) **Compositional:** that aspect which is concerned with part-whole structure of an experience.
- 2) **Sensual:** the 'look and feel' of a physical (or virtual) artifact. The sensations in an experience might range from fear, thrill to excitement.
- 3) **Emotional:** the emotional thread ranges from joy, anger, desperation and so on. Emotions are not just passive responses to a certain situation; they can also be the 'drive' or the motivational aspect of the experience itself.
- 4) **Spatio-temporal:** all types of experience unfold in a particular time and place; this is what Wright et al describes as the spatio-temporal thread.

User experience design

How can we make sense of experience, for the sake of the user experience and Experience Design? According to Norman (2008), Forlizzi (2000) and Hassenzahl (2003), user experience could be defined as perceptions and answers obtained throughout use and anticipation of use of a certain product or service. As mentioned before, components like emotions, composition, senses and space are intrinsic of any kind of experience. It is also important to mention that any type of previous experience before the actual and present experience could influence the appraisal of use. In other terms, the experience itself could be completely different according to previous exposed information.

Figure 1: Time spans of user experience. (Dagstuhl Seminar on Demarcating User Experience, 2011)

User experience it is about an encounter with a system, it has a beginning and an end; it relies upon memories and perceptions in order to provide the

outcome, the feedback, the experience. As shown above, the time spans of user experience can be divided in four moments: Anticipated UX, Momentary UX, Episodic UX and Cumulative UX.

EXPERIENCE DESIGN

The Experience economy context proposed by Pine and Gilmore (1998), in which a new era of modern consumerism was being developed, suggests that the success of entrepreneurs could be achievable by creating and staging memorable experiences to the consumers. The authors claim that experiences are not static; they are dynamic, real and most importantly they should not be treated as a commodity. To stage and deliver memorable experiences, one should carefully plan its projects alongside a more innovative approach, such as combining efforts with areas like Design Research, Marketing and so on.

McLellan (2000) suggests that Experience Design is the creation of an effective space between a user (to achieve a certain goal) and a context. The major goal of Experience Design would be to orchestrate experiences that are functional, engaging, attractive and memorable. And in order to reach that goal one should pay extra attention to the minimum details of an experience.

For this research, we chose to investigate the emotion component of an experience, more precisely, the emotions involved in food experiences. We believe that with a better planning, design and execution, we could offer food experiences that are more enjoyable, more emotional (in a positive way) and long lasting. Therefore we will now discuss how emotions are or can be elucidated and how the Design field could be aided with the results.

EMOTIONS

In favor of how designers might approach their projects regarding the emotional aspect, it is relevant to understand what in fact emotions are and how these types of responses occur. Izard (1977) discusses that emotions cannot be treated as a single phenomenon, they cannot be defined with just an emotional experience report and they also cannot be only defined for the electrophysiological responses from the nervous system. The author suggests three main topics to define emotions: the experience or

conscious state of an emotion; the process occurring in the brain and nervous system; observation of body and facial expressions regarding emotional manifestation.

Regarding how emotions are or could be evoked, we will rely upon Izard (1977), Lazarus & Averill (1972), Tomkins (1962) and Desmet (2002) theories. These authors suggest that emotions could be the result of an appraisal between interaction or perception of a user and a certain context. According to Tomkins (1962), emotions could also be triggered upon certain stimulation (mental state, image, action). It is based on the appraisal theory and potential emotional triggers that we built our experiments on this research.

EMOTIONAL TRIGGERS

Tomkins (1962) mentions in his research that emotions are activated upon changes on the density of the neural stimulation and that such changes could be initiated by triggers. According to his theory, these triggers could influence individual emotional states. He considers images, emotional states, motivation and previous emotions to be potential emotional triggers. In a related topic, Sengers (2003) discusses the perspective of the arts and humanities area where it suggests that trying to formally an experience is futile. Many humanists and artists defend the idea that complexity, mess, enigmas are vital to the human nature of being and thus, any formal representation would not be truthful to the event. So, the idea behind our experiments is not to try the representation of complexity, instead we tried to trigger it inside the mind of the user. By doing that we are dealing with his expectations, perceptions and potential emotional responses.

DESIGN EMOTION

Norman (2008) discusses that humans are complex animals with even more complex structures: they are conscious of their role in the world and are capable of reflecting upon past experiences for the sake of learning and future success. The Design Emotion field of research has the purpose of understand the role of emotions inside this complex reality and aid designers in pursuance of better and innovative emotional designs

Figure 2: Model of appraisal Desmet and Hekkert (2002).

Desmet and Hekkert (2002) claim that we could design a certain object to evoke neutral emotions, it is, however, uncertain that the product would actually evoke neutral emotions. The appraisal involves cognitive processing of the user's concerns and the product (including performance, aesthetics, and usability) in order to obtain a certain emotional response.

EMOTIONAL SCALES

In order to evaluate the emotions evoked during the food experiences, we chose and adapted King and Meiselman's (2010) EsSence Profile tool of measuring emotions. We considered that the EsSence Profile tool was complete enough to answer our questions, and it was specifically developed for food quality and preference studies.

Our adaptation is justified by the fact that it is not part of this study to identify and quantify specific emotions. It was, in fact, to understand if there would be a difference of intensity between positive and negative emotions. Thereunto we reduced the number of emotions, always keeping in mind the range that would be available to our interviewees express their emotional states.

That said, these were the emotions that were evaluated on the experiment I (in alphabetical order):

Feeling	Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely
Active					
Adventurous					
Affectionate					
Agressive					
Bored					
Challenged					
Complete					
Disgusted					
Eager					
Energetic					
Enthusiastic					
Free					
Friendly					
Glad					
Good-natured					
Guilty					
Happy					
Interested					
Loving					
Mild					
Nostalgic					
Peaceful					
Pleased					
Polite					
Quiet					
Satisfied					
Steady					
Understanding					
Worried					

Table 1: Scale of emotions adapted from King and Meiselman (2010).

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EXPECTATION AND PERCEPTION

Expectation can be described as subjective notions of things or events that are about to come. A expectative it is like a hypothesis formulated by an individual and his final response will be given upon his appraisal and perception accordingly to the experience that has transpired.

Perceptions can be described as individual mental impressions of a certain object, product or stimulation. According to Anderson (1973), perception presents itself with four major characteristics: it is selective, relates to symbols and meanings, depends on stimuli and could be influenced by personal motives.

Whenever a user tries a certain food product in real, daily contexts, his perception towards the product it is not only based on the sensorial characteristics. His perception is composed by many factors, including ideas and beliefs regarding the properties of the product, also information received from third parties such as advertising and word-of-mouth play a major role on building his response towards the actual performance. These types of information are stored on our memory and will be used whenever another experience is about to happen.

Whether we have already stored information about a certain product or not, there are at least five theories (Anderson, 1973) that explain our expectation behavior regarding product performance evaluation:

cognitive dissonance, contrast, generalized negativism, assimilation-contrast and prospect theory.

Cognitive dissonance

According to Festinger's (1957) Theory, cognitive dissonance could be considered as a type of unconfirmed expectancy. Whenever a certain cognitive element complements the information once stored in one's memory we say that there is consistency. When these chains of events are not connected due to incongruities of memory and actual performance or perception, we say that there is dissonance. The cognitive dissonance creates a psychological state of discomfort in which the user is forced to evaluate the incongruities of the experience towards reducing or distorting some of the information in order to make as close as what one had expected. An example of cognitive dissonance is expressed in the fable The Fox and the Grapes by Aesop. In the story, a fox encounters some grapes and wishes to eat them. When the fox realizes that the grapes are too far away for him to reach, he decides that the fruits are not worth eating, with the justification that the grapes are probably sour anyway. The cognitive dissonance is explained through a pattern of actions: the fox desires the fruit, finds it unattainable, and reduces his dissonance by criticizing it.

Contrast

When expectations are not met with the actual performance of a certain product, the contrast theory presumes that the surprise or contrast between expectation and result will cause an effect of exaggeration. An example of the theory is going to watch a movie after you hear excellent reviews about it. If you don't think that the movie was worth the reviews that you have heard, you might rate it worse than if you had actually gone to the movies without knowing any of that information in the first place.

Generalized negativity

Product perception will always be negative when there is disparity between expectations and actual product performance, and the degree of negativity will vary directly with the amount of disparity.

Assimilation-contrast

The assimilation-contrast theory derives from the social psychology studies, in which Hovland, Harvey and Sherif (1957) investigated under which conditions individuals would accept certain aspects that differed from their own opinions. This theory suggests that individuals have ranges or latitudes of acceptance, rejection and neutrality. The discrepancy between expectation and performance of the product would be responsible for categorizing the experience or performance as accepted, rejected or neutral. The theory also defends that the higher the discrepancy, the higher the probability of rejection would be.

Prospect Theory

According to Kahneman and Tversky (1979), the Prospect Theory suggests that the subjective value of gain is smaller than the subjective value of loss. People will make decisions based on the potential value of losses and gains rather than the final outcome. In other words, when a user expects less from a certain situation and receives more, he will gain – his experience was better than expected. When a user has high expectations from a certain situation and receives less, he will lose – his experience was worse than expected.

METHODOLOGY

To answer our initial question: if it is possible to develop or enhance emotional triggers for food experiences, we developed a set of two experiments and one survey.

EXPERIMENT I

In our initial experiment, we manipulated the variable taste. We were inspired by chef's Heston Blumenthal (2008) work, in which he developed a set of fake fruits: the aesthetics simulated a fresh fruit, but the inside was filled with a meat compound. In our experiment, we developed similar fake fruits; in this case, we created fake grapes. The casing was made from gelatin, agar-agar and purple coloring. The filling was made of condensed milk and sugar, forming a rich and creamy paste, as shown in the picture below.

Figure 3: The fake grape. Font: Authors.

To test if the manipulation of the variable taste could trigger emotional responses on our users, we interviewed 60 individuals, divided into two groups: control and experimental. The experiment group was conducted in a waiting room, located at the Unisinos Design Campus in Porto Alegre.

The participants were told that we were collecting data for a food preference study. Furthermore, they were asked to enter the room and fill out a questionnaire about personal information regarding food preferences. To give the idea that they were going to taste a grape, a bowl containing a real fruit was being displayed in front of the interviewee while they were filling out the initial questionnaire, as the photo below illustrates. After they finished filling out the form, they were asked to move to another table, taste the fake grape and answer another questionnaire regarding their emotions elucidated during the experiment. We repeated the same script for the control group, except that we switched to real, regular grapes instead of fake ones.

Figure 4: Questionnaire and real fruit.

Results Experiment I

Maximum value for mean = 5.00

Descriptive Statistics Experimental Group		
Group	Mean	Std. Deviation
Affectionate	2.63	1.326
Aggressive	1.13	.507
Mild	2.30	1.291
Friendly	3.20	1.186
Loving	3.27	1.337
Joyful	4.10	.960
Eager	2.40	1.303
Adventurous	3.10	1.447
Pleased	3.77	1.223
GoodNatured	2.97	1.426
Calm	3.57	1.305
Whole	3.07	1.337
Understanding	3.10	1.373
Merry	4.00	1.174
Guilty	1.17	.592
Challenged	2.97	1.520
Polite	3.00	1.438
Peaceful	3.40	1.404
Energetic	2.80	1.157
Disgusted	1.13	.571
Bored	1.27	.907
Enthusiastic	3.57	1.251
Happy	3.90	1.155
Steady	2.87	1.306
Interested	4.57	.817
Free	3.77	1.357
Nostalgic	1.93	1.172
Worried	1.30	.466
Quiet	2.30	1.149
Satisfied	4.17	1.085
Secure	3.63	1.377
Texture	4.17	1.177
Color	4.00	1.114
Smell	2.77	1.501
Taste	4.50	.861
Interaction	3.40	1.476
FoodPreference	3.47	1.525
Memory	4.27	.785

Table 1: Descriptive statistics for Experimental Group

**Descriptive Statistics
Control Group**

Group	Mean	Std. Deviation
Affectionate	2.27	1.048
Aggressive	1.07	.365
Mild	2.13	.973
Friendly	2.57	1.223
Loving	2.43	1.165
Joyful	2.63	1.299
Eager	1.43	.817
Adventurous	2.00	1.017
Pleased	3.50	1.009
GoodNatured	3.07	1.311
Calm	3.07	1.172
Whole	2.80	1.095
Understanding	2.70	1.208
Merry	3.33	1.155
Guilty	1.20	.551
Challenged	1.87	1.042

Polite	2.37	1.245
Peaceful	2.93	1.172
Energetic	2.40	1.070
Disgusted	1.31	.761
Bored	1.07	.254
Enthusiastic	2.47	1.358
Happy	3.07	1.285
Steady	3.00	1.114
Interested	3.07	1.112
Free	3.07	1.258
Nostalgic	1.87	1.196
Worried	1.07	.254
Quiet	1.67	.959
Satisfied	3.47	1.042
Secure	3.00	1.203
Texture	3.37	.999
Color	3.37	.964
Smell	3.30	1.179
Taste	3.73	1.143
Interaction	2.77	1.165
FoodPreference	3.13	1.137
Memory	3.70	1.022

Table 2: Descriptive statistics for Experimental Group

Emotion	Sig.
Loving	.006
Joyful	.000
Eager	.002
Adventurous	.002
Merry	.025
Challenged	.002
Enthusiastic	.004
Happy	.008
Interested	.000
Worried	.027
Quiet	.044
Satisfied	.023
Texture	.005
Color	.018
Taste	.005
Interaction	.046
Memory	.019

Table 3: Anova for Experimental and Control Group

Our findings show that it is possible to achieve more intensive positive emotions while manipulating the variable taste. Emotions like Loving, Joyful, Adventurous, Merry, Challenged, Enthusiastic, Happy, Steady, Worried (as in less worried) were all significant $p < 0.05$. Other items questioned such Texture, Color, Taste and Memory (memory of product) was also significant with $p < 0.05$. According to the theories discussed earlier on, we believe that the disconfirmation of expectancies could be interesting topics to designers focus on. More specifically, the assimilation-contrast theory is particularly relevant due to the nature of the

discrepancy being small enough so the performance of the product would fall upon the latitude of acceptance and not rejection. If the discrepancy presented itself with a particular large variance, the performance of the product could fall upon the rejection latitude, thus the experience itself would evoke more negative emotions rather than positive ones.

EXPERIMENT II

In our second experiment, we manipulated the variable sound. More specifically, we added the variable sound to a specific food experience: soup. This experiment was also inspired upon chef's Heston Blumenthal from the restaurant The Fat Duck. In his restaurant, Blumenthal (2008) created a dish called Sound of the Sea trying to represent the sound and taste of the sea. The dish was made of toasted grains, miso oil, malt dextrin and a seaweed consommé, as shown in the picture below:

Figure 5: Sound of the Sea. Blumenthal (2008)

The innovative aspect of this dish is that it was served with a pair of earphones. They were presented to the client inside a seashell and connected to them was an iPod, which would play the sound of the sea, in order to match the taste presented.

Figure 6: Sound of the Sea – earphones. Blumenthal (2008)

To evaluate the sound variable and if it was capable of evoking more intensive positive emotions, we decided to present our participants with a clean and simple version of the dish. To guarantee that no other stimulation would influence the interviewees, we chose the Laboratory of Sensorial Analysis located at the Unisinos Gastronomy Campus to carry out the experiment.

The Laboratory of Sensorial Analysis has individual cabins that are only accessible through a window (for the conductor of the experiment) or its back (where the participant sit down). This setup provided the conductor of the experiment freedom and security to run the data collection without any sort of third party influence.

Regarding the food preparation, we chose an industrial type of seafood consommé called Hondashi. It is worldwide available - mainly in Asian cuisine grocery stores. The reason behind our choice is that by evaluating an industrial type of consommé, it would be easier for other researchers to replicate this experiment.

The sounds that we chose for the experiment were two: Forest and Sea. We believed that the experiences with sound would be more enjoyable and with more intense positive emotions. To measure the intensity of them, we reduced the scale used in the experiment I. By reducing the number of emotions, we eliminated a problem encountered during experiment I: the length of the questionnaire and the number of

emotions questioned could be influencing our participants in a negative way. Therefore, we reduced the set of emotions to eleven, always respecting the range of emotions that would be available to the participant express their emotional state after the experiment.

Questionnaire Experiment II

Evaluate all emotions according to your experience, following the criteria below:

Emotion	Not at all	Slightly	Moderate	Very	Extremely
Disgusted					
Happy					
Aggressive					
Bored					
Worried					
Nostalgic					
Interested					
Secure					
Free					
Challenged					
Calm					

Table 5: Emotions scale adapted from Experiment 1.

Mark the expression that best represents your experience:

Figure 7: Expression scale.

We asked our participants to sit down one at a time and taste the consommé (presented in a plain, white small bowl). If the participant was from the control group, no sound stimulation was added. However, if they were part of the forest or sea group, the conductor of the experiment would hand a pair of earphones to the participant wear during the food experience. We interviewed 30 participants for each group, totalizing 90.

Results Experiment II

Descriptive Statistics for Control Group^a

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Disgusted	30	1.90	.960
Happy	30	2.40	1.070
Aggressive	30	1.23	.817
Bored	30	2.07	1.112
Worried	30	2.17	1.167
Nostalgic	30	1.87	1.042
Interested	30	2.60	1.070
Secure	30	2.47	1.196
Free	30	2.47	1.279
Challenged	30	2.27	1.285
Calm	30	2.63	1.189
Pleasantness of experience	30	4.23	1.888
Valid N (listwise)	30		

a. Group = Control

Maximum value for Pleasantness = 7.00

Maximum value for means of emotion = 5.00

Table 6: Descriptive statistics for Control Group

Descriptive Statistics for Forest Group^a

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Disgusted	30	1.27	.828
Happy	30	3.00	.830
Aggressive	30	1.20	.610
Bored	30	1.60	.675
Worried	30	1.90	.960
Nostalgic	30	1.93	.980
Interested	30	3.13	1.137
Secure	30	2.63	1.129
Free	30	3.07	1.202
Challenged	30	2.97	1.273
Calm	30	3.57	.935
Pleasantness of experience	30	5.27	1.048
Valid N (listwise)	30		

a. grupos = Forest

Maximum value for Pleasantness = 7.00

Maximum value for means of emotion = 5.00

Table 7: Descriptive statistics for Forest Group

Descriptive Statistics for Sea Group^a

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Disgusted	30	1.17	.592
Happy	30	3.03	.964
Aggressive	30	1.20	.551
Bored	30	1.33	.661
Worried	30	1.50	.731
Nostalgic	30	2.37	1.245
Interested	30	3.60	1.037
Secure	30	3.33	1.061
Free	30	3.57	1.073
Challenged	30	2.93	1.388
Calm	30	3.90	1.094
Pleasantness of experience	30	5.93	.868
Valid N (listwise)	30		

a. grupo = Sea

Maximum value for Pleasantness = 7.00

Maximum value for means of emotion = 5.00

Table 8: Descriptive statistics for Sea Group

One way ANOVA for Control and Sea Groups

	Sig.
Disgusted	.001
Happy	.019
Aggressive	.854
Bored	.003
Worried	.010
Nostalgic	.097
Interested	.001
Secure	.004
Free	.001
Challenged	.058
Calm	.000
Pleasantness of experience	.000

Table 9: Anova for Control and Sea groups.

According to our data, we verified that in the majority of the emotions evaluated the higher means were found in the Sea Group. This includes variables like Happy, Bored (as in less bored), Worried (as in less worried), Interested, Secure, Free, Calm and Pleasantness of experience.

We also found significant data when using One way ANOVA to compare means. In the Control versus Sea Group, we found $p < 0.05$ for Disgusted, Happy,

One way ANOVA for Control and Forest Groups

	Sig.
Disgusted	.008
Happy	.018
Aggressive	.859
Bored	.054
Worried	.331
Nostalgic	.799
Interested	.066
Secure	.581
Free	.066
Challenged	.038
Calm	.001
Pleasantness of experience	.011

Table 10: Anova for Control and Forest Groups.

One way ANOVA for Sea and Forest Groups

	Sig.
Disgusted	.592
Happy	.886
Aggressive	1.000
Bored	.127
Worried	.075
Nostalgic	.140
Interested	.102
Secure	.016
Free	.094
Challenged	.923
Calm	.210
Pleasantness of experience	.010

Table 11: Anova for Sea and Forest groups.

Bored, Worried, Interested, Secure, Free, Calm and Pleasantness of experience. After checking the descriptive statistics for both groups, we concluded that the experience for the sea group was far more pleasant against the control group. It was also evident that the positive emotions (with $p < 0.05$) were more intense for the sea group.

The data also concludes that even though the forest group didn't have the highest means for positive

emotions, it was still more positive while comparing to the control group. The same aspect was shown in Pleasantness of experience, even though the forest sound it was not congruent with the dish proposed, the experience itself was more enjoyable than the control group one.

SURVEY

The survey we carried out as our final data collection aimed for association between shapes, tastes and emotions. There are many researchers that approached these themes on the past few years, only a few though aimed to correlate the 3 variables mentioned above. One particular study that inspired our survey was the Bouba and Kiki effect (Ramachandran and Hubbard, 2001). In this particular study, the researchers asked several students from USA and India to name with Bouba or Kiki these two geometrical forms as shown below:

Figure 8: Bouba and kiki effect. (Ramachandran and Hubbard, 2001)

Therefore we ask our readers, which one do you think it is Bouba and which one it is Kiki?

The authors found out that in the majority of cases (95% for USA and 98% for India), the rounded shape was named Bouba, while the pointy shape was named Kiki. From these results and others (Köhler, 1929; Maurer 2006), the authors proposed theories that the human brain is capable of extracting abstract properties from shapes and sounds. One of the explanations for these results is that when someone pronounces Bouba, the mouth would make a more rounded shape in order to produce that sound, while a more taut, angular mouth shape is needed to make the sound kiki. The sound of the letter B is softer compared to the K, as well. These authors also

suggests the presence of synesthesia-like mappings, which are likely to be the neurological basis for sound symbolism, in which sounds are associated to object and events in the world. Thereunto, if our brain is actually capable of making such associations, it would be reasonable to suggest that we could also make associations between shapes, tastes and why not – emotions.

Having that said, we built two questions for our survey: first we asked our participants to associate shapes to taste and then shapes to emotions. The set of shapes selected for this questionnaire is composed mainly with basic geometrical forms: square, circle, triangle (represented by a star), free form and spiral. The set of emotions used were the same used to evaluate the experiment II.

The platform used to collect responses to our questionnaires was the Qualtrics.com website. The number of responses we received, excluding the ones that were incomplete or invalid, summed 250.

Survey results

Our findings show that it might be possible to correlate tastes, shapes and emotions to a certain extension. The frequencies regarding positive emotions and tastes like sweet, spicy, salty and sour are encouraging enough in a way that our future work may be towards this direction. It is unclear, however, why some of the negative emotions were mostly associated with Do Not Apply, one might say that it is easier to face and deal with positive emotions, while negative ones on the other hand might be a bit more complex. The Do Not Apply frequencies under tastes also presented us with fairly intriguing data. Bitter and Sour were the most voted items with Do Not Apply. This result might be associated with the fact that historically humans did not feed themselves with sour or bitter ingredients. Those types of taste were mainly associated with spoiled, fermented or poisonous items. Humans are naturally predisposed to eat things that are sweet because they can provide enough energy to sustain a certain individual.

# n=250	Answer In %	Circle (1)	Square (2)	Star (3)	Spiral (4)	Free Form (5)	Do Not Apply
2	Happy	11,13	1,75	25,92	2,52	10,26	1,08
8	Secure	22,47	19,5	2,64	0,63	2,97	2,52
11	Calm	22,05	4,75	2,16	1,05	18,9	3,96
4	Bored	9,24	23,75	0,96	6,93	6,48	6,12
9	Free	6,3	1,75	6,24	14,28	18,09	6,84
6	Nostalgic	7,56	4,75	6,96	6,09	21,6	8,28
5	Worried	3,15	17	4,56	11,76	7,56	10,8
7	Interested	11,13	5	17,28	4,2	4,86	12,6
1	Disgusted	1,68	6,25	1,92	24,99	3,78	15,48
10	Challenged	2,94	7	15,12	13,02	2,43	15,84
3	Aggressive	1,26	6,5	14,64	14,49	2,97	15,84

Table 12: Association between emotions and geometrical forms.

# n=250	Answer In %	Circle (1)	Square (2)	Star (3)	Spiral (4)	Free Form (5)	Do Not Apply
1	Salty	23,65	35,64	6,96	5,76	5,4	9,35
2	Acid	4,3	7,2	21,75	22,4	9	15,4
3	Sweet and Sour	18,92	7,2	8,41	15,36	23,85	17,05
4	Spicy	1,29	6,12	39,15	15,04	3,6	7,15
5	Sweet	42,57	2,16	4,06	2,56	42,3	2,2
6	Bitter	4,73	27,72	6,96	15,68	7,65	23,1
7	Sour	4,3	12,96	13,05	22,4	6,75	25,85

Table 13. Association between taste and geometrical forms.

DISCUSSION

To correlate our three data collections and to answer our initial and main topic of discussion we will discuss the theory behind our experiments and the survey that was carried out. Regarding emotional triggers we could affirm that it is possible to develop, enhance or adapt such a component in order to promote better emotional food experiences.

The experiments that were held collected significant data to support the theories suggested by Anderson (1973), Desmet and Schifferstein (2008) and Tomkins (1962). This means that it is possible for designers to focus on intangible aspects of food experiences, such as expectancies, perception and phases of user experience.

Figure 9: Expectation and Appraisal model.

The main aspect of experiment I was to discuss if by manipulating the variable taste, positive emotions would be elucidated in a stronger sense. The results can be explained through the assimilation-contrast theory, which suggests that users might be aware of a certain fluctuation of performance of products, and would ignore small deviations from what they were expecting. In this case, if the discrepancy between the expectation and performance is sufficiently small (or large enough), the product might fall upon the latitude of acceptance and by contrast, it would also be significantly better than what they expected, labeling the experience as more enjoyable, more emotional and more positive.

As seen on figure 09, the discrepancy level might influence the appraisal according to one's expectancies. That appraisal could lead to positive or negative emotions according to the degree or threshold of discrepancy (figure 10 and figure 11).

Figure 10: Threshold of discrepancy.

Regarding the second experiment, we found out that sound stimuli are capable of enhancing food experiences. Even though the forest sound was not congruent with the dish proposed, it was still better

than expected by the participants. This means that food experiences could be enhanced to a certain extent by applying sound stimulation. It would be better, though, if the sound stimulation was chosen to match the food that was being served, as seen with the Sea Group. However, it remains unanswered what would it be the saturation point, in other words, how much stimulation would still be acceptable by the users while maintaining the positive feedback of the food experience. As Sengers (2003) discussed, instead of representing complexity, we should trigger it in the mind of the user.

Figure 11: Possible outcomes regarding the discrepancy of expectations.

This complexity may be tied with our last data collection, our survey. Our results showed that it is possible to correlate shapes, tastes and emotions to a certain extent. If we take what we have concluded so far, it would be possible to start designing a framework for the development of emotional triggers for food experiences that involves expectations, perception and sensorial associations (e.g. shapes with taste).

LIMITATIONS

Our research was fortunate conduct experiments in a controlled environment. We encourage fellow researchers to test and analyze the emotions evoked in different contexts with and without stimulation (such as sound or scent). Another topic to keep in mind is the association between geometrical forms, emotions and taste.

Why do most people associate square forms with salty foods and emotions like Bored and Safe? What

would happen if we design triggers to break that expectation? Would be acceptable to add stimulation such as scent or sound? What kind of experience would that be?

While some of these questions remain unanswered, we believe that designers are capable of taking this matter onto the next level. It is by understanding our user, his beliefs and concerns that we will become more apt to deliver better, more enjoyable and more emotional food experiences.

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